

GENERALIZATIONS OF FUZZY QUASI OPEN SETS AND CONNECTEDNESS BETWEEN FUZZY SETS IN FUZZY BITOPOLOGICAL SPACES

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Abstract. In this paper we introduce and study fuzzy quasi e (resp. e^* , a , β , δs and δp)-open sets, fuzzy quasi e (resp. e^* , a , β , δs and δp)-closed sets, fuzzy quasi e (resp. e^* , a , β , δs and δp)-connectedness between fuzzy sets, fuzzy quasi e (resp. e^* , a , β , δs and δp)-separated sets in fuzzy bitopological spaces.

1. INTRODUCTION

The concept of fuzzy set was introduced by Zadeh [29] provided a natural foundation for building new branches in mathematics. Fuzzy sets have applications in many fields such as information [23] and control [24]. In 1968 Chang [6] introduced fuzzy topological space using fuzzy sets. Kandil [14] defined and studied the concept of fuzzy bitopological spaces as a generalization of bitopological spaces [16] in fuzzy setting. Since then many results from classical topology are being extended in both fuzzy topological and fuzzy bitopological spaces ([3], [4], [12], [14], [15], [18]-[21], [28]) and their properties were also investigated. The initiations of e -open sets, e^* -open sets and a -open sets in topological spaces are due to Ekici [[9],[10],[11]]. In fuzzy topology, e -open sets were introduced by Seenivasan in 2015 [22]. In 1971 Datta [7] introduced and studied quasi semiopen sets in bitopological spaces. Using it concepts of fuzzy quasi semiopen sets and connectedness between fuzzy sets in fuzzy bitopological spaces were defined and studied [26]. The purpose of this paper is to generalize some of the concepts of [8, 13, 25] in fuzzy bitopological spaces using fuzzy e (resp. e^* , a , β , δs and δp)-open sets.

2. PRELIMINARIES

We recall the following definition.

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Definition 2.1. A fuzzy subset λ in an fts (X, τ) is called fuzzy regular open (*fro*, for short) [2] if $\lambda = IntCl(\lambda)$ and a regular closed set if $\lambda = ClInt(\lambda)$.

Definition 2.2. [22] The fuzzy δ interior of subset λ of X is the union of all fuzzy regular open sets contained in λ and fuzzy δ closure of subset λ of X is the intersection of all fuzzy regular closed sets containing λ .

Definition 2.3. [27] A subset λ is called fuzzy δ open if $\lambda = \delta Int(\lambda)$. The complement of fuzzy δ open set is called fuzzy δ closed (i.e., $\lambda = \delta Cl(\lambda)$.)

Definition 2.4. A subset λ is called fuzzy δ -pre open [1] (resp. fuzzy δ -semi open [17], fuzzy e -open [22]) if $\lambda \leq IntCl_\delta(\lambda)$ (resp. $\lambda \leq ClInt_\delta(\lambda)$, $\lambda \leq IntCl_\delta(\lambda) \vee ClInt_\delta(\lambda)$)

Definition 2.5. [1, 17, 22] The complement of a fuzzy δ -preopen set (resp. fuzzy δ -semiopen set, fuzzy e -open) is called fuzzy δ -preclosed (resp. fuzzy δ -semiclosed, fuzzy e -closed).

Definition 2.6. [1, 17, 22] The intersection of all fuzzy δ -preclosed (resp. fuzzy δ -semiclosed, fuzzy e -closed) sets containing λ is called fuzzy δp (resp. δs , e)-closure of λ and is denoted by $f\delta pCl(\lambda)$ (resp. $f\delta sCl(\lambda)$, $feCl(\lambda)$) and the union of all fuzzy δ -preopen (resp. fuzzy δ -semiopen, fuzzy e -open) sets contained in λ is called fuzzy δp (resp. δs , e)-interior of λ and is denoted by $f\delta pInt(\lambda)$ (resp. $f\delta sInt(\lambda)$, $feInt(\lambda)$).

Definition 2.7. A fuzzy bitopological space [14] (in short fbts) in an ordered triple (X, τ_1, τ_2) where τ_1 and τ_2 are fuzzy topologies on X and the members of τ_1 (or τ_2) are called τ_1 -fuzzy (or τ_2 -fuzzy) open sets.

A fuzzy set λ in a fbts (X, τ_1, τ_2) is called τ_i -fuzzy closed if its complement $1 - \lambda$ or λ' is τ_i -fuzzy open for $i = 1, 2$.

Definition 2.8. [5] In a fbts (X, τ_1, τ_2) a fuzzy set λ is said to be fuzzy quasi-open (in short *fqo*) if $\lambda = \mu \vee \eta$ for some $\mu \in \tau_1$ and $\eta \in \tau_2$.

In this paper we shall denote the family of τ_i -fuzzy e (resp. e^* , a , β , δs and δp)-open (τ_i -fuzzy e (resp. e^* , a , β , δs and δp)-closed) sets in fbts (X, τ_1, τ_2) by τ_i^{feo} (resp. $\tau_i^{fe^*o}$, τ_i^{fao} , $\tau_i^{f\beta o}$, $\tau_i^{f\delta so}$ and $\tau_i^{f\delta po}$) (τ_i^{fec} (resp. $\tau_i^{fe^*c}$, τ_i^{fac} , $\tau_i^{f\beta c}$, $\tau_i^{f\delta sc}$ and $\tau_i^{f\delta pc}$)) for $i = 1, 2$.

3. FUZZY QUASI e (RESP. e^* , a , β , δs AND δp)-OPEN SETS IN FUZZY BITOPOLOGICAL SPACES

Definition 3.1. In a fbts (X, τ_1, τ_2) a fuzzy set λ is said to be fuzzy quasi e (resp. e^* , a , β , δs and δp)-open (in short *fqeo*) (resp., in short *fqe^*o*, *fqa o* , *fq β o*, *fq δ so* and *fq δ po*)) if $\lambda = \mu \vee \eta$ for some $\mu \in \tau_1^{feo}$ and $\eta \in \tau_2^{feo}$ (resp. $\mu \in \tau_1^{fe^*o}$ and $\eta \in \tau_2^{fe^*o}$, $\mu \in \tau_1^{fao}$ and $\eta \in \tau_2^{fao}$, $\mu \in \tau_1^{f\beta o}$ and $\eta \in \tau_2^{f\beta o}$, $\mu \in \tau_1^{f\delta so}$ and $\eta \in \tau_2^{f\delta so}$, $\mu \in \tau_1^{f\delta po}$ and $\eta \in \tau_2^{f\delta po}$).

Remark.

- (i) Every fuzzy quasi-open set is fuzzy quasi e -open sets.
- (ii) Every fuzzy quasi-open set is fuzzy quasi δ -semi open sets.

- (iii) Every fuzzy quasi-open set is fuzzy quasi δ -pre open sets.
- (iv) Every fuzzy quasi δ -semi open and quasi δ -pre open set is fuzzy quasi e -open sets.
- (v) Every fuzzy quasi a -open set is fuzzy quasi e -open sets.
- (vi) Every fuzzy quasi a -open set is fuzzy quasi β -open sets.
- (vii) Every fuzzy quasi e -open set is fuzzy quasi β -open sets.
- (viii) Every fuzzy quasi e^* -open set is fuzzy quasi β -open sets.

But the converse is not true as shown in the following Examples.

Example 3.2. Let $X = \{a, b, c, d\}$, $\tau_1 = \{0, 1, \mu_1, \mu_2, \mu_3, \mu_4\}$ and $\tau_2 = \{0, 1, \eta_1, \eta_2, \eta_3\}$ where $\mu_1, \mu_2, \mu_3, \mu_4, \eta_1, \eta_2, \eta_3 : X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ are defined as follows: $\mu_1 = \frac{0}{a} + \frac{0.1}{b} + \frac{1}{c} + \frac{1}{d}$, $\mu_2 = \frac{0}{a} + \frac{0.4}{b} + \frac{0}{c} + \frac{0}{d}$, $\mu_3 = \frac{0}{a} + \frac{0.4}{b} + \frac{1}{c} + \frac{1}{d}$, $\mu_4 = \frac{0}{a} + \frac{0.1}{b} + \frac{0}{c} + \frac{0}{d}$, $\eta_1 = \frac{0}{a} + \frac{0.3}{b} + \frac{0}{c} + \frac{0}{d}$, $\eta_2 = \frac{0}{a} + \frac{0}{b} + \frac{1}{c} + \frac{1}{d}$, $\eta_3 = \frac{0}{a} + \frac{0.3}{b} + \frac{1}{c} + \frac{1}{d}$. Then (X, τ_1, τ_2) is a fpts with fuzzy topologies τ_1 and τ_2 . Let λ be a fuzzy set in X defined as $\lambda : X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ such that (i) $\lambda = \frac{0}{a} + \frac{0.7}{b} + \frac{1}{c} + \frac{1}{d}$. But $\lambda = \mu_5 \vee \eta_5$ where $\mu_5 = \frac{0}{a} + \frac{0.5}{b} + \frac{1}{c} + \frac{1}{d} \in \tau_1^{fgeo}$ and $\eta_5 = \frac{0}{a} + \frac{0.7}{b} + \frac{0}{c} + \frac{0}{d} \in \tau_2^{fgeo}$, therefore, λ is $fgeo$, but it is not fuzzy quasi-open and fuzzy quasi a -open. (ii) $\lambda = \frac{1}{a} + \frac{0.4}{b} + \frac{0.4}{c} + \frac{0.4}{d}$. But $\lambda = \mu \vee \eta$ where $\mu = \frac{1}{a} + \frac{0.4}{b} + \frac{0}{c} + \frac{0}{d} \in \tau_1^{fq\beta o}$ and $\eta = \frac{0}{a} + \frac{0}{b} + \frac{0.4}{c} + \frac{0.4}{d} \in \tau_2^{fq\beta o}$, therefore, λ is $fq\beta o$, but it is not fqe^*o and $fqao$. (iii) $\lambda = \frac{0.7}{a} + \frac{0.7}{b} + \frac{1}{c} + \frac{1}{d}$. But $\lambda = \mu \vee \eta$ where $\mu = \frac{0}{a} + \frac{0.5}{b} + \frac{1}{c} + \frac{1}{d} \in \tau_1^{fgeo}$ and $\eta = \frac{0.7}{a} + \frac{0.7}{b} + \frac{0}{c} + \frac{0}{d} \in \tau_2^{fgeo}$, therefore, λ is $fgeo$, but it is not $fq\delta po$ and $fq\delta so$. (iv) $\lambda = \frac{0}{a} + \frac{0.4}{b} + \frac{1}{c} + \frac{1}{d}$. But $\lambda = \mu \vee \eta$ where $\mu = \frac{0}{a} + \frac{0.4}{b} + \frac{1}{c} + \frac{1}{d} \in \tau_1^{fq\delta po}$ (resp. $\in \tau_1^{fq\delta so}$) and $\eta = \frac{0}{a} + \frac{0.2}{b} + \frac{0}{c} + \frac{0}{d} \in \tau_2^{fq\delta po}$ (resp. $\in \tau_1^{fq\delta so}$) therefore, λ is $fq\delta po$ and $fq\delta so$, but it is not fqo .

Example 3.3. Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$, $\tau_1 = \{0, 1, \mu_1, \mu_2, \mu_3, \mu_4\}$ and $\tau_2 = \{0, 1, \eta_1, \eta_2, \eta_3\}$ where $\mu_1, \mu_2, \mu_3, \mu_4, \eta_1, \eta_2, \eta_3 : X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ are defined as follows: $\mu_1 = \frac{0.7}{a} + \frac{1}{b} + \frac{0}{c}$, $\mu_2 = \frac{0.2}{a} + \frac{0}{b} + \frac{1}{c}$, $\mu_3 = \frac{0.7}{a} + \frac{1}{b} + \frac{1}{c}$, $\mu_4 = \frac{0.2}{a} + \frac{0}{b} + \frac{0}{c}$, $\eta_1 = \frac{0}{a} + \frac{0.3}{b} + \frac{0}{c}$, $\eta_2 = \frac{0}{a} + \frac{0}{b} + \frac{1}{c}$, $\eta_3 = \frac{0}{a} + \frac{0.3}{b} + \frac{1}{c}$. Then (X, τ_1, τ_2) is a fpts with fuzzy topologies τ_1 and τ_2 . Let λ be a fuzzy set in X defined as $\lambda : X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ such that $\lambda = \frac{0.3}{a} + \frac{0}{b} + \frac{0.2}{c}$. But $\lambda = \mu \vee \eta$ where $\mu = \frac{0.2}{a} + \frac{0}{b} + \frac{0.1}{c} \in \tau_1^{fq\beta o}$ and $\eta = \frac{0.3}{a} + \frac{0}{b} + \frac{0.2}{c} \in \tau_2^{fq\beta o}$, therefore, λ is $fq\beta o$, but it is not $fgeo$.

Remark. Fuzzy quasi e -open set and fuzzy quasi e^* -open sets are independent.

Example 3.4. In Example 3.2, $\lambda = \frac{1}{a} + \frac{0.4}{b} + \frac{0.4}{c} + \frac{0.4}{d}$. But $\lambda = \mu \vee \eta$ where $\mu = \frac{1}{a} + \frac{0.4}{b} + \frac{0}{c} + \frac{0}{d} \in \tau_1^{fgeo}$ and $\eta = \frac{0}{a} + \frac{0}{b} + \frac{0.4}{c} + \frac{0.4}{d} \in \tau_2^{fgeo}$, therefore, λ is $fgeo$, but it is not fqe^*o .

Example 3.5. In Example 3.3, $\lambda = \frac{0.3}{a} + \frac{0}{b} + \frac{0.2}{c}$. But $\lambda = \mu \vee \eta$ where $\mu = \frac{0.2}{a} + \frac{0}{b} + \frac{0.1}{c} \in \tau_1^{f e^* o}$ and $\eta = \frac{0.3}{a} + \frac{0}{b} + \frac{0.2}{c} \in \tau_2^{f e^* o}$, therefore, λ is fqe^*o , but it is not $fgeo$.

All above discussed interrelation can be put together in an arrow diagram is given as follows.

Proposition 3.1. A fuzzy set λ in a fbts (X, τ_1, τ_2) is

- (i) $fgeo$ iff $\lambda = eInt_{\tau_1}(\lambda) \vee eInt_{\tau_2}(\lambda)$.
- (ii) fqe^*o iff $\lambda = e^*Int_{\tau_1}(\lambda) \vee e^*Int_{\tau_2}(\lambda)$.
- (iii) $fqao$ iff $\lambda = aInt_{\tau_1}(\lambda) \vee aInt_{\tau_2}(\lambda)$.
- (iv) $fq\beta o$ iff $\lambda = \beta Int_{\tau_1}(\lambda) \vee \beta Int_{\tau_2}(\lambda)$.
- (v) $fq\delta so$ iff $\lambda = \delta sInt_{\tau_1}(\lambda) \vee \delta sInt_{\tau_2}(\lambda)$.
- (vi) $fq\delta po$ iff $\lambda = \delta pInt_{\tau_1}(\lambda) \vee \delta pInt_{\tau_2}(\lambda)$.

Proof. Prove the first part only the other cases are similar.

(i) Suppose λ is $fgeo$ set in fbts (X, τ_1, τ_2) . Then, by definition, we have

$$\lambda = \mu \vee \eta \quad (3.1)$$

for some $\mu \in \tau_1^{feo}$ and $\eta \in \tau_2^{feo}$.

From (3.1), $\mu = eInt_{\tau_1}(\lambda)$, $\eta = eInt_{\tau_2}(\lambda)$ and so $\lambda = eInt_{\tau_1}(\lambda) \vee eInt_{\tau_2}(\lambda)$.

Conversely, suppose that $\lambda = eInt_{\tau_1}(\lambda) \vee eInt_{\tau_2}(\lambda) = \lambda_1 \vee \lambda_2$ (say) where $\lambda_1 = eInt_{\tau_1}(\lambda)$ and $\lambda_2 = eInt_{\tau_2}(\lambda)$. Clearly λ_1 and λ_2 are τ_1 -fuzzy e -open and τ_2 -fuzzy e -open sets respectively. Therefore λ is $fgeo$ set. \square

Remark.

- (i) Every τ_1 -fuzzy e -open (or τ_2 -fuzzy e -open) sets is $fgeo$ set.
- (ii) Every τ_1 -fuzzy a -open (or τ_2 -fuzzy a -open) sets is $fqao$ set.
- (iii) Every τ_1 -fuzzy e^* -open (or τ_2 -fuzzy e^* -open) sets is fqe^*o set.
- (iv) Every τ_1 -fuzzy β -open (or τ_2 -fuzzy β -open) sets is $fq\beta o$ set.
- (v) Every τ_1 -fuzzy δp -open (or τ_2 -fuzzy δp -open) sets is $fq\delta po$ set.
- (vi) Every τ_1 -fuzzy δs -open (or τ_2 -fuzzy δs -open) sets is $fq\delta so$ set.

But the converse is not true as shown in the following Example ??.

Example 3.6. In Example 3.2, let λ be a fuzzy set in X defined as $\lambda : X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ such that $\lambda = \frac{0}{a} + \frac{0.7}{b} + \frac{1}{c} + \frac{1}{d}$. But $\lambda = \mu_5 \vee \eta_4$ where $\mu_5 \in \tau_1^{feo}$ and $\eta_4 \in \tau_2^{feo}$, therefore, λ is $fgeo$, but it is not τ_2 -fuzzy e -open set.

Example 3.7. In Examples 3.3 and 3.9, let λ be a fuzzy set in X defined as $\lambda : X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ such that (i) $\lambda = \frac{0.6}{a} + \frac{1}{b} + \frac{1}{c}$. But $\lambda = \mu_5 \vee \eta_4$ where $\mu_5 \in \tau_1^{fe^*o}$ and $\eta_4 \in \tau_2^{fe^*o}$, therefore, λ is fqe^*o , but it is not τ_2 -fuzzy e^* -open set.

(ii) $\lambda = \frac{0.5}{a} + \frac{1}{b} + \frac{1}{c}$. But $\lambda = \mu_6 \vee \eta_5$ where $\mu_6 \in \tau_1^{f\beta o}$ and $\eta_5 \in \tau_2^{f\beta o}$, therefore, λ is $fq\beta o$, but it is not τ_2 -fuzzy β -open set.

(iii) $\lambda = \frac{0.1}{a} + \frac{0}{b} + \frac{1}{c}$. But $\lambda = \mu_7 \vee \eta_2$ where $\mu_7 \in \tau_1^{fao}$ and $\eta_2 \in \tau_2^{fao}$, therefore, λ is $fqao$, but it is not τ_2 -fuzzy a -open set.

(iv) $\lambda = \frac{0.5}{a} + \frac{1}{b} + \frac{1}{c}$. But $\lambda = \mu_6 \vee \eta_6$ where $\mu_6 \in \tau_1^{f\delta po}$ and $\eta_6 \in \tau_2^{f\delta po}$, therefore, λ is $fq\delta po$, but it is not τ_2 -fuzzy δp -open set.

(v) $\lambda = \frac{0.1}{a} + \frac{0}{b} + \frac{1}{c}$. But $\lambda = \mu_6 \vee \eta_2$ where $\mu_6 \in \tau_1^{f\delta so}$ and $\eta_2 \in \tau_2^{f\delta so}$, therefore, λ is $fq\delta so$, but it is not τ_2 -fuzzy δs -open set.

Proposition 3.2. Arbitrary union of $fgeo$ (resp. fqe^*o , $fqao$, $fq\beta o$, $fq\delta so$, $fq\delta po$) sets is a $fgeo$ (resp. fqe^*o , $fqao$, $fq\beta o$, $fq\delta so$, $fq\delta po$) set.

Proof. Let λ_i , $i \in I$ be $fgeo$ sets in a fts X . To prove that $\bigvee_{i \in I} \lambda_i$ is $fgeo$ set. Let $\bigvee_{i \in I} \lambda_i = \lambda_1 \vee \lambda_2 \vee \dots = (\mu_1 \vee \eta_1) \vee (\mu_2 \vee \eta_2) \dots = \bigvee_{i \in I} (\mu_i \vee \eta_i)$ as $\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \dots$ are $fgeo$ set. Then $\bigvee_{i \in I} \lambda_i = \bigvee_{i \in I} (\mu_i \vee \eta_i) = (\bigvee_{i \in I} \mu_i) \vee (\bigvee_{i \in I} \eta_i)$ for some $\bigvee_{i \in I} \mu_i \in T_1^{feo}$ and $\bigvee_{i \in I} \eta_i \in T_2^{feo}$

$\bigvee_{i \in I} \eta_i \in T_2^{feo}$. Hence $\bigvee_{i \in I} \lambda_i$ is $fqeo$ set. Thus arbitrary union of $fqeo$ sets is a $fqeo$ set. \square

The proof of the other cases are similar.

Remark. If λ_1 and λ_2 are two $fqeo$ (resp. fqe^*o , fqa , fqb , $fqdso$, $fqdpo$) sets in a fbts (X, τ_1, τ_2) then $\lambda_1 \wedge \lambda_2$ need not be $fqeo$ (resp. fqe^*o , fqa , fqb , $fqdso$, $fqdpo$) as shown in the following Examples 3.8 and 3.9.

Example 3.8. In Example 3.2, let $\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \mu_5, \mu_6, \eta_4$ and η_5 be two fuzzy sets on X and are defined as $\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \mu_5, \mu_6, \eta_4, \eta_5 : X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ such that $\lambda_1 = \frac{0}{a} + \frac{0.7}{b} + \frac{1}{c} + \frac{1}{d}$, $\lambda_2 = \mu_6 = \frac{0.1}{a} + \frac{0.5}{b} + \frac{1}{c} + \frac{1}{d}$, $\mu_5 = \frac{0}{a} + \frac{0.5}{b} + \frac{1}{c} + \frac{1}{d}$, $\eta_4 = \frac{0}{a} + \frac{0.7}{b} + \frac{1}{c} + \frac{1}{d}$ and $\eta_5 = \frac{0}{a} + \frac{0.4}{b} + \frac{0}{c} + \frac{1}{d}$. As $\lambda_1 = \mu_5 \vee \eta_4$, $\mu_5 \in \tau_1^{feo}$ and $\eta_4 \in \tau_2^{feo}$, and $\lambda_2 = \mu_6 \vee \eta_5$, $\mu_6 \in \tau_1^{feo}$, and $\eta_5 \in \tau_2^{feo}$, λ_1 and λ_2 are fuzzy quasi e -open ($fqeo$) sets in X . However $\lambda_1 \wedge \lambda_2 = \lambda$ (say) where $\lambda = \frac{0}{a} + \frac{0.5}{b} + \frac{1}{c} + \frac{1}{d}$, is not equal to $\mu \vee \eta$ for some $\mu \in \tau_1^{feo}$ and $\eta \in \tau_2^{feo}$, which shows that $\lambda_1 \wedge \lambda_2$ is not $fqeo$ set in X . Hence the Remark 3

Example 3.9. In Example 3.3, let $\lambda_1 = \mu_3, \lambda_2 = \mu_5, \mu_6, \mu_7, \mu_8, \mu_9, \eta_4, \eta_5$ and η_6 be two fuzzy sets on X and are defined as $\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \eta_4 : X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ such that $\lambda_2 = \mu_5 = \frac{0.6}{a} + \frac{1}{b} + \frac{1}{c}$, $\mu_6 = \frac{0.5}{a} + \frac{1}{b} + \frac{1}{c}$, $\mu_7 = \frac{0.1}{a} + \frac{0}{b} + \frac{0}{c}$, $\mu_8 = \frac{0.9}{a} + \frac{1}{b} + \frac{0}{c}$, $\mu_9 = \frac{0.1}{a} + \frac{0}{b} + \frac{1}{c}$, $\eta_4 = \frac{0.2}{a} + \frac{0.1}{b} + \frac{0}{c}$, $\eta_5 = \frac{0.3}{a} + \frac{0.2}{b} + \frac{0}{c}$ and $\eta_6 = \frac{0}{a} + \frac{0.2}{b} + \frac{0}{c}$.

(i) As $\lambda_1 = \mu_3 \vee \eta_4$, $\mu_3 \in \tau_1^{fe^*o}$ and $\eta_4 \in \tau_2^{fe^*o}$, and $\lambda_2 = \mu_5 \vee \eta_4$, $\mu_5 \in \tau_1^{fe^*o}$, and $\eta_4 \in \tau_2^{fe^*o}$, λ_1 and λ_2 are fuzzy quasi e^* -open (fqe^*o) sets in X . However $\lambda_1 \wedge \lambda_2 = \lambda$ (say) where $\lambda = \frac{0.6}{a} + \frac{1}{b} + \frac{1}{c}$, is not equal to $\mu \vee \eta$ for some $\mu \in \tau_1^{fe^*o}$ and $\eta \in \tau_2^{fe^*o}$, which shows that $\lambda_1 \wedge \lambda_2$ is not fqe^*o set in X .

(ii) As $\lambda_1 = \mu_3 \vee \eta_5$, $\mu_3 \in \tau_1^{f\beta o}$ and $\eta_5 \in \tau_2^{f\beta o}$, and $\lambda_2 = \mu_6 \vee \eta_5$, $\mu_6 \in \tau_1^{f\beta o}$, and $\eta_5 \in \tau_2^{f\beta o}$, λ_1 and λ_2 are fuzzy quasi β -open (fqb) sets in X . However $\lambda_1 \wedge \lambda_2 = \lambda$ (say) where $\lambda = \frac{0.5}{a} + \frac{1}{b} + \frac{1}{c}$, is not equal to $\mu \vee \eta$ for some $\mu \in \tau_1^{f\beta o}$ and $\eta \in \tau_2^{f\beta o}$, which shows that $\lambda_1 \wedge \lambda_2$ is not fqb set in X .

(iii) As $\lambda_1 = \mu_7 \vee \eta_2$, $\mu_7 \in \tau_1^{fa o}$ and $\eta_2 \in \tau_2^{fa o}$, and $\lambda_2 = \mu_2 \vee \eta_2$, $\mu_2 \in \tau_1^{fa o}$, and $\eta_2 \in \tau_2^{fa o}$, λ_1 and λ_2 are fuzzy quasi a -open (fqa) sets in X . However $\lambda_1 \wedge \lambda_2 = \lambda$ (say) where $\lambda = \frac{0.1}{a} + \frac{0}{b} + \frac{1}{c}$, is not equal to $\mu \vee \eta$ for some $\mu \in \tau_1^{fa o}$ and $\eta \in \tau_2^{fa o}$, which shows that $\lambda_1 \wedge \lambda_2$ is not fqa set in X .

(iv) As $\lambda_1 = \mu_3 \vee \eta_6$, $\mu_3 \in \tau_1^{f\delta p o}$ and $\eta_6 \in \tau_2^{f\delta p o}$, and $\lambda_2 = \mu_6 \vee \eta_6$, $\mu_6 \in \tau_1^{f\delta p o}$, and $\eta_6 \in \tau_2^{f\delta p o}$, λ_1 and λ_2 are fuzzy quasi δp -open ($fqdpo$) sets in X . However $\lambda_1 \wedge \lambda_2 = \lambda$ (say) where $\lambda = \frac{0.5}{a} + \frac{1}{b} + \frac{1}{c}$, is not equal to $\mu \vee \eta$ for some $\mu \in \tau_1^{f\delta p o}$ and $\eta \in \tau_2^{f\delta p o}$, which shows that $\lambda_1 \wedge \lambda_2$ is not $fqdpo$ set in X .

(v) As $\lambda_1 = \mu_8 \vee \eta_2$, $\mu_8 \in \tau_1^{f\delta s o}$ and $\eta_2 \in \tau_2^{f\delta s o}$, and $\lambda_2 = \mu_9 \vee \eta_2$, $\mu_9 \in \tau_1^{f\delta s o}$, and $\eta_2 \in \tau_2^{f\delta s o}$, λ_1 and λ_2 are fuzzy quasi δs -open ($fqdso$) sets in X . However $\lambda_1 \wedge \lambda_2 = \lambda$ (say) where $\lambda = \frac{0.1}{a} + \frac{0}{b} + \frac{1}{c}$, is not equal to $\mu \vee \eta$ for some $\mu \in \tau_1^{f\delta s o}$ and $\eta \in \tau_2^{f\delta s o}$, which shows that $\lambda_1 \wedge \lambda_2$ is not $fqdso$ set in X . Hence the Remark 3

Definition 3.10. A fuzzy set λ in a fbts (X, τ_1, τ_2) is said to be fuzzy quasi e (resp. e^* , a , β , δp and δs)-closed (in short fqc) (resp. in short, fqc^* , fqb , fqa , $fqdsc$, $fqdpc$) iff its complement $1 - \lambda$ or λ' is $fqeo$ (in short fqe^*o , fqb , fqa , $fqdso$, $fqdpo$) set.

Remark. Every τ_1 -fuzzy e (resp. e^* , a , β , δp and δs)-closed (or τ_2 -fuzzy e (resp. e^* , a , β , δp and δs)-closed) set in any fbts (X, τ_1, τ_2) is fuzzy quasi e (resp. e^* , a , β , δp and δs)-closed.

Remark. Finite intersection of $fqec$ (resp. fqe^*c , $fqac$, $fq\beta c$, $fq\delta pc$ and $fq\delta sc$) sets is also a $fqec$ (resp. fqe^*c , $fqac$, $fq\beta c$, $fq\delta pc$ and $fq\delta sc$) set.

Definition 3.11. Let λ be a fuzzy set in fbts (X, τ_1, τ_2) . Then fuzzy quasi e -closure and fuzzy quasi e -interior of λ , denoted by $fqeCl(\lambda)$ and $fqeInt(\lambda)$ respectively, are defined as follows:

- (1) $fqeCl(\lambda) = \wedge\{\delta : \delta \text{ is } fqec \text{ set and } \delta \geq \lambda\}$
- (2) $fqeInt(\lambda) = \vee\{\eta : \eta \text{ is } fgeo \text{ set and } \eta \leq \lambda\}$

In fact a fuzzy set λ in a fbts (X, τ_1, τ_2) is

- (1) $fqec$ iff $\lambda = fqeCl(\lambda)$,
- (2) $fgeo$ iff $\lambda = fqeInt(\lambda)$.

In a similar way we can define fqe^*Cl , $fqaCl$, $fq\beta Cl$, $fq\delta pCl$ and $fq\delta sCl$ (resp. fqe^*Int , $fqaInt$, $fq\beta Int$, $fq\delta pInt$ and $fq\delta sInt$).

Remark. The interrelation between $fqeCl(\lambda)$ and $fqeInt(\lambda)$ are given as follows:

- (i) $1 - fqeCl(\lambda) = 1 - \wedge\{\delta : \delta \text{ is } fqec \text{ set and } \delta \geq \lambda\}$
 $= \vee\{\delta' : \delta' \text{ is } fgeo \text{ set and } \delta' \leq \lambda'\}$.

Thus $1 - fqeCl(\lambda) = fqeInt(\lambda')$.

- (ii) $1 - fqeInt(\lambda) = 1 - \vee\{\eta : \eta \text{ is } fgeo \text{ set and } \eta \leq \lambda\}$
 $= \wedge\{\eta' : \eta' \text{ is } fqec \text{ set and } \eta' \geq \lambda'\}$.

Thus $1 - fqeInt(\lambda) = fqeCl(\lambda')$. In a similar way we relate the interrelation between other generalized sets also.

Definition 3.12. A fuzzy set λ in a fbts (X, τ_1, τ_2) is said to be (τ_1, τ_2) -fuzzy e (resp. e^* , a , β , δp and δs)-clopen (resp. (τ_2, τ_1) -fuzzy e (resp. e^* , a , β , δp and δs)-clopen) set if it is τ_1 -fuzzy e (resp. e^* , a , β , δp and δs)-closed and τ_2 -fuzzy e (resp. e^* , a , β , δp and δs)-open (resp. τ_2 -fuzzy e (resp. e^* , a , β , δp and δs)-closed and τ_1 -fuzzy e (resp. e^* , a , β , δp and δs)-open).

Definition 3.13. A fuzzy set λ in a fbts (X, τ_1, τ_2) is said to be fuzzy e (resp. e^* , a , β , δp and δs)-biclopen if it is both (τ_1, τ_2) -fuzzy e (resp. e^* , a , β , δp and δs)-clopen as well as (τ_2, τ_1) -fuzzy e (resp. e^* , a , β , δp and δs)-clopen set.

Definition 3.14. In a fbts (X, τ_1, τ_2) a fuzzy quasi e (resp. e^* , a , β , δp and δs)-clopen set means a set which is both fuzzy quasi e (resp. e^* , a , β , δp and δs)-closed as well as fuzzy quasi e (resp. e^* , a , β , δp and δs)-open.

Remark. Every (τ_1, τ_2) -fuzzy e (resp. e^* , a , β , δp and δs)-clopen (resp., (τ_2, τ_1) -fuzzy e (resp. e^* , a , β , δp and δs)-clopen) set is fuzzy quasi e (resp. e^* , a , β , δp and δs)-clopen. But the converse is not true as shown by Example ??

Example 3.15. In Example 3.2, let μ be a fuzzy set on X defined as $\mu : X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ such that $\mu = \frac{0}{a} + \frac{0.7}{b} + \frac{1}{c} + \frac{1}{d}$. Then μ is fuzzy quasi e -clopen in the fbts (X, τ_1, τ_2) . But it is not (τ_1, τ_2) -fuzzy e -clopen.

Example 3.16. In Example 3.3, let μ be a fuzzy set on X defined as $\mu : X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ such that (i) $\mu = \frac{0.6}{a} + \frac{1}{b} + \frac{1}{c}$. Then μ is fuzzy quasi e^* -clopen in the fbts (X, τ_1, τ_2) . But it is not (τ_1, τ_2) -fuzzy e^* -clopen.

- (ii) $\mu = \frac{0.5}{a} + \frac{1}{b} + \frac{1}{c}$. Then μ is fuzzy quasi β (resp. δp)-clopen in the fbts (X, τ_1, τ_2) . But it is not (τ_1, τ_2) -fuzzy β (resp. δp)-clopen.
- (iii) $\mu = \frac{0.1}{a} + \frac{0}{b} + \frac{1}{c}$. Then μ is fuzzy quasi a (resp. δs)-clopen in the fbts (X, τ_1, τ_2) . But it is not (τ_1, τ_2) -fuzzy a (resp. δs)-clopen.

4. FUZZY QUASI e (RESP. e^* , a , β , δp AND δs)-CONNECTEDNESS BETWEEN FUZZY SETS

Definition 4.1. A fbts (X, τ_1, τ_2) is said to be (τ_1, τ_2) -fuzzy e (resp. e^* , a , β , δp and δs)-connected between some fuzzy sets λ_1 and λ_2 if there exists no (τ_1, τ_2) -fuzzy e (resp. e^* , a , β , δp and δs)-clopen set μ such that $\lambda_1 \leq \mu \leq 1 - \lambda_2$. Further (X, τ_1, τ_2) is said to be pairwise fuzzy e (resp. e^* , a , β , δp and δs)-connected between the fuzzy sets λ_1 and λ_2 if it is (τ_1, τ_2) -fuzzy e (resp. e^* , a , β , δp and δs)-connected as well as (τ_2, τ_1) -fuzzy e (resp. e^* , a , β , δp and δs)-connected between λ_1 and λ_2 .

Example 4.2. In Examples 3.8 and 3.9 is an example of pairwise fuzzy e -connected.

Definition 4.3. A fbts (X, τ_1, τ_2) is said to be fuzzy quasi e (resp. e^* , a , β , δp and δs)-connected between its fuzzy sets λ_1 and λ_2 , if it has no fuzzy quasi e (resp. e^* , a , β , δp and δs)-clopen set μ such that $\lambda_1 \leq \mu \leq 1 - \lambda_2$.

Remark. The implications contained in the following diagram are true and the reverse implications need not be true as shown in the following examples.

Example 4.4. In Example 3.3, let λ_1 and λ_2 be two fuzzy sets on X defined as $\lambda_1, \lambda_2 : X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ such that (i) $\lambda_1(x) = \frac{0.7}{a} + \frac{0.8}{b} + \frac{0}{c}$ and $\lambda_2(x) = \frac{0.2}{a} + \frac{0}{b} + \frac{1}{c}$. We note that $\mu = \frac{0.7}{a} + \frac{0.9}{b} + \frac{0}{c}$ is fuzzy quasi e (resp. δs and δp)-connected but not fuzzy quasi (resp. e^*)-connected. Since $\lambda_1 \leq \mu \leq 1 - \lambda_2$, we can conclude that (X, τ_1, τ_2) is not (τ_1, τ_2) fuzzy quasi connected between λ_1 and λ_2 . But, as there is no (τ_1, τ_2) -fuzzy clopen set μ satisfying $\lambda_1 \leq \mu \leq 1 - \lambda_2$, (X, τ_1, τ_2) is not fuzzy quasi (resp. e^*)-connected.

(ii) $\lambda_1(x) = \frac{0.4}{a} + \frac{0}{b} + \frac{0.6}{c}$ and $\lambda_2(x) = \frac{0.3}{a} + \frac{0}{b} + \frac{0.2}{c}$. We note that $\mu = \frac{0.6}{a} + \frac{0}{b} + \frac{0.8}{c}$ is fuzzy quasi e^* (resp. β)-connected but not fuzzy quasi e -connected. Since $\lambda_1 \leq \mu \leq 1 - \lambda_2$, we can conclude that (X, τ_1, τ_2) is not (τ_1, τ_2) fuzzy quasi e -connected between λ_1 and λ_2 .

(iii) $\lambda_1(x) = \frac{0.7}{a} + \frac{0.5}{b} + \frac{0}{c}$ and $\lambda_2(x) = \frac{0.2}{a} + \frac{0.3}{b} + \frac{0.9}{c}$. We note that $\mu = \frac{0.7}{a} + \frac{0.6}{b} + \frac{0}{c}$ is fuzzy quasi e -connected but not fuzzy quasi δp -connected. Since $\lambda_1 \leq \mu \leq 1 - \lambda_2$, we can conclude that (X, τ_1, τ_2) is not (τ_1, τ_2) fuzzy quasi δp -connected between λ_1 and λ_2 .

(iv) $\lambda_1(x) = \frac{0.5}{a} + \frac{0.2}{b} + \frac{0.3}{c}$ and $\lambda_2(x) = \frac{0.3}{a} + \frac{0.5}{b} + \frac{0.5}{c}$. We note that $\mu = \frac{0.5}{a} + \frac{0.4}{b} + \frac{0.3}{c}$ is fuzzy quasi β -connected but not fuzzy quasi e^* -connected. Since $\lambda_1 \leq \mu \leq 1 - \lambda_2$, we can conclude that (X, τ_1, τ_2) is not (τ_1, τ_2) fuzzy quasi e^* -connected between λ_1 and λ_2 .

Example 4.5. Let $X = \{a, b, c, d\}$, $\tau_1 = \{0, 1, \mu_1, \mu_2, \mu_3, \mu_4\}$ and $\tau_2 = \{0, 1, \eta_1, \eta_2, \eta_3\}$ where $\mu_1, \mu_2, \mu_3, \mu_4, \eta_1, \eta_2, \eta_3 : X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ are defined as follows: $\mu_1 = \frac{0}{a} + \frac{0.1}{b} + \frac{1}{c} + \frac{1}{d}$, $\mu_2 = \frac{0}{a} + \frac{0.4}{b} + \frac{0}{c} + \frac{0}{d}$, $\mu_3 = \frac{0}{a} + \frac{0.4}{b} + \frac{1}{c} + \frac{1}{d}$, $\mu_4 = \frac{0}{a} + \frac{0.1}{b} + \frac{0}{c} + \frac{0}{d}$, $\eta_1 = \frac{1}{a} + \frac{0.7}{b} + \frac{1}{c} + \frac{1}{d}$, $\eta_2 = \frac{1}{a} + \frac{1}{b} + \frac{0}{c} + \frac{0}{d}$, $\eta_3 = \frac{1}{a} + \frac{0.7}{b} + \frac{0}{c} + \frac{0}{d}$. Then (X, τ_1, τ_2) is a fbts with fuzzy topologies τ_1 and τ_2 . Let λ_1 and λ_2 be two fuzzy sets on X defined as $\lambda_1, \lambda_2 : X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ such that $\lambda_1(x) = \frac{0}{a} + \frac{0.4}{b} + \frac{0}{c} + \frac{0}{d}$ and $\lambda_2(x) = \frac{0}{a} + \frac{0.2}{b} + \frac{0.8}{c} + \frac{0.8}{d}$. We note that $\mu = \frac{1}{a} + \frac{0.6}{b} + \frac{0}{c} + \frac{0}{d}$ is fuzzy quasi e (resp. β)-connected but not fuzzy quasi a -connected. Since $\lambda_1 \leq \mu \leq 1 - \lambda_2$, we can conclude that (X, τ_1, τ_2) is not (τ_1, τ_2) fuzzy quasi e (resp. β)-connected between λ_1 and λ_2 .

Example 4.6. Let $X = \{a, b\}$, $\tau_1 = \{0, 1, \mu_1, \mu_2\}$ and $\tau_2 = \{0, 1, \eta_1, \eta_2\}$ where $\mu_1, \mu_2, \eta_1, \eta_2 : X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ are defined as follows: $\mu_1 = \frac{0.2}{a} + \frac{0.1}{b}$, $\mu_2 = \frac{0}{a} + \frac{0.1}{b}$, $\eta_1 = \frac{0.3}{a} + \frac{0.1}{b}$, $\eta_2 = \frac{0.2}{a} + \frac{0.1}{b}$. Then (X, τ_1, τ_2) is a fbts with fuzzy topologies τ_1 and τ_2 . Let λ_1 and λ_2 be two fuzzy sets on X defined as $\lambda_1, \lambda_2 : X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ such that $\lambda_1(x) = \frac{0.4}{a} + \frac{0.4}{b}$ and $\lambda_2(x) = \frac{0.2}{a} + \frac{0.3}{b}$. We note that $\mu = \frac{0.6}{a} + \frac{0.7}{b}$ is fuzzy quasi e -connected but not fuzzy quasi δs -connected.

Proposition 4.1. If a fbts (X, τ_1, τ_2) is fuzzy quasi e -connected between its fuzzy sets λ_1 and λ_2 and if $\lambda_1 \leq \eta_1$ and $\lambda_2 \leq \eta_2$, then (X, τ_1, τ_2) is fuzzy quasi e -connected between fuzzy sets η_1 and η_2 .

Proof. Suppose (X, τ_1, τ_2) is not fuzzy quasi e -connected between fuzzy sets η_1 and η_2 . Then it has fuzzy quasi e -clopen set μ such that

$$\eta_1 \leq \mu \leq 1 - \eta_2. \tag{4.1}$$

By construction we have, $\lambda_1 \leq \eta_1$ and $\lambda_2 \leq \eta_2$. From (1) we get $\lambda_1 \leq \eta_1$ implies

$$\lambda_1 \leq \mu. \tag{4.2}$$

And also $\lambda_2 \leq \eta_2$ gives

$$1 - \lambda_2 \geq 1 - \eta_2 \geq \mu \Rightarrow 1 - \lambda_2 \geq \mu$$

$$(i.e) \mu \leq 1 - \lambda_2. \tag{4.3}$$

From (4.1) and (4.2) we get $\lambda_1 \leq \mu \leq 1 - \lambda_2$. This shows (X, τ_1, τ_2) is not fuzzy quasi e -connected between fuzzy sets λ_1 and λ_2 , a contradiction. Hence the proposition is proved. \square

Proposition 4.2. If a fbts (X, τ_1, τ_2) is fuzzy quasi e^* (resp. $a, \beta, \delta p$ and δs)-connected between its fuzzy sets λ_1 and λ_2 and if $\lambda_1 \leq \eta_1$ and $\lambda_2 \leq \eta_2$, then (X, τ_1, τ_2) is fuzzy quasi e (resp. $a, \beta, \delta p$ and δs)-connected between fuzzy sets η_1 and η_2 .

Proof. Follows from Proposition 4.1 \square

Proposition 4.3. A fbts (X, τ_1, τ_2) is fuzzy quasi e -connected between fuzzy sets λ_1 and λ_2 iff it is fuzzy quasi e -connected between $fqcI(\lambda_1)$ and $fqcI(\lambda_2)$.

Proof. Sufficiency: Suppose (X, τ_1, τ_2) is not fuzzy quasi e -connected between fuzzy sets λ_1 and λ_2 . Then X has fuzzy quasi e -clopen set μ such that $\lambda_1 \leq \mu \leq 1 - \lambda_2$.

Thus we have, $\lambda_1 \leq \mu$ and $\mu \leq 1 - \lambda_2$. Now $\lambda_1 \leq \mu$ implies $fqcCl(\lambda_1) \leq fqcCl(\mu) = \mu$, as μ is fuzzy quasi e -closed.

$$i.e \ fqcCl(\lambda_1) \leq \mu. \quad (4.4)$$

Also $\mu \leq 1 - \lambda_2$ implies $\mu = fqeInt(\mu) \leq fqeInt(1 - \lambda_2) = 1 - fqcCl(\lambda_2)$ as μ is fuzzy quasi e -open.

$$i.e \ \mu \leq 1 - fqcCl(\lambda_2). \quad (4.5)$$

From 4.4 and 4.5 we get $fqcCl(\lambda_1) \leq \mu \leq 1 - fqcCl(\lambda_2)$. This shows that (X, T_1, T_2) is not fuzzy quasi e -connected between fuzzy sets $fqcCl(\lambda_1)$ and $fqcCl(\lambda_2)$.

Necessity: Suppose (X, τ_1, τ_2) is not fuzzy quasi e -connected between $fqcCl(\lambda_1)$ and $fqcCl(\lambda_2)$. Then X has fuzzy quasi e -clopen set μ such that $fqcCl(\lambda_1) \leq \mu \leq 1 - fqcCl(\lambda_2)$

Now $\lambda_1 \leq fqcCl(\lambda_1) \leq \mu$ implies

$$\lambda_1 \leq \mu. \quad (4.6)$$

Also, $\mu \leq 1 - fqcCl(\lambda_2)$. But $fqcCl(\lambda_2) \geq \lambda_2$ which implies $1 - fqcCl(\lambda_2) \leq 1 - \lambda_2$.

Therefore, $\mu \leq 1 - fqcCl(\lambda_2) \leq 1 - \lambda_2$

$$i.e \ \mu \leq 1 - \lambda_2 \quad (4.7)$$

Combining (4.6) and (4.7) we get $\lambda_1 \leq \mu \leq 1 - \lambda_2$. This shows that (X, τ_1, τ_2) is not fuzzy quasi e -connected between λ_1 and λ_2 . \square

Proposition 4.4. A fbts (X, τ_1, τ_2) is fuzzy quasi e^* (resp. $a, \beta, \delta p$ and δs)-connected between fuzzy sets λ_1 and λ_2 iff it is fuzzy quasi e^* (resp. $a, \beta, \delta p$ and δs)-connected between $fqe^*Cl(\lambda_1)$ and $fqe^*Cl(\lambda_2)$ (resp. $fqaCl(\lambda_1)$ and $fqaCl(\lambda_2)$, $fq\beta Cl(\lambda_1)$ and $fq\beta Cl(\lambda_2)$, $fq\delta p Cl(\lambda_1)$ and $fq\delta p Cl(\lambda_2)$, $fq\delta s Cl(\lambda_1)$ and $fq\delta s Cl(\lambda_2)$).

Proof. Follows from Proposition 4.3 \square

Proposition 4.5. If a fbts (X, τ_1, τ_2) is fuzzy quasi e -connected neither between λ_1 and η_1 nor between λ_1 and η_2 then it is not fuzzy quasi e -connected between λ_1 and $\eta_1 \vee \eta_2$.

Proof. Suppose (X, τ_1, τ_2) is fuzzy quasi e -connected neither between λ_1 and η_1 nor between λ_1 and η_2 . Then it has fuzzy quasi e -clopen sets μ_1, μ_2 such that

$$\lambda_1 \leq \mu_1 \leq 1 - \eta_1 \text{ and } \lambda_1 \leq \mu_2 \leq 1 - \eta_2. \quad (4.8)$$

Now, put $\mu_1 \wedge \mu_2 = \mu$. Then, $\lambda_1 \wedge \lambda_1 \leq \mu_1 \wedge \mu_2 \leq (1 - \eta_1) \wedge (1 - \eta_2) \Rightarrow \lambda_1 \leq \mu \leq 1 - (\eta_1 \vee \eta_2)$, which shows that (X, τ_1, τ_2) is not fuzzy quasi e -connected between λ_1 and $\eta_1 \vee \eta_2$. \square

Proposition 4.6. If a fbts (X, τ_1, τ_2) is fuzzy quasi e^* (resp. $a, \beta, \delta p$ and δs)-connected neither between λ_1 and η_1 nor between λ_1 and η_2 then it is not fuzzy quasi e^* (resp. $a, \beta, \delta p$ and δs)-connected between λ_1 and $\eta_1 \vee \eta_2$.

Proof. Follows from Proposition 4.5 \square

Definition 4.7. A fbts (X, τ_1, τ_2) is said to be fuzzy quasi e (resp. $e^*, a, \beta, \delta p$ and δs)-connected iff it has no proper fuzzy set which is both fuzzy quasi e (resp. $e^*, a, \beta, \delta p$ and δs)-open and fuzzy quasi e (resp. $e^*, a, \beta, \delta p$ and δs)-closed.

Equivalently, a fbts (X, τ_1, τ_2) is said to be fuzzy quasi e (resp. e^* , a , β , δp and δs)-connected iff it has no proper fuzzy quasi e (resp. e^* , a , β , δp and δs)-clopen set.

Proposition 4.7. A fbts (X, τ_1, τ_2) is fuzzy quasi e -connected iff X has no proper fuzzy sets λ_1 and λ_2 , which are fuzzy quasi e -open sets such that $\lambda_1 + \lambda_2 = 1$.

Proof. Necessity: Suppose (X, τ_1, τ_2) is not fuzzy quasi e -connected. Then X has proper fuzzy set λ_1 , which is both fuzzy quasi e -open and fuzzy quasi e -closed. Take $1 - \lambda_1 = \lambda_2$. Since λ_1 is fuzzy quasi e -closed λ_2 is $fqeo$ set. Then $\lambda_1 + \lambda_2 = 1$.

Sufficiency: Suppose that fbts (X, τ_1, τ_2) has $fqeo$ sets λ_1 and λ_2 , such that $\lambda_1 + \lambda_2 = 1$. Then $\lambda_1 = 1 - \lambda_2$ is fuzzy quasi e -closed set. Similarly, λ_2 is also fuzzy quasi e -closed. Hence (X, τ_1, τ_2) is not fuzzy quasi e -connected. \square

Proposition 4.8. A fbts (X, τ_1, τ_2) is fuzzy quasi e^* (resp. a , β , δp and δs)-connected iff X has no proper fuzzy sets λ_1 and λ_2 , which are fuzzy quasi e^* (resp. a , β , δp and δs)-open sets such that $\lambda_1 + \lambda_2 = 1$.

Proof. Follows from Proposition 4.7 \square

Proposition 4.9. A fbts (X, τ_1, τ_2) is said to be fuzzy quasi e -connected iff it is fuzzy quasi e -connected between each pair of its non-zero fuzzy sets λ_1 and λ_2 .

Proof. Necessity: Let λ_1 and λ_2 be any a pair of non-zero fuzzy sets on X . Suppose (X, τ_1, τ_2) is not fuzzy quasi e -connected between λ_1 and λ_2 . Then it has fuzzy quasi e -clopen set μ such that $\lambda_1 \leq \mu \leq 1 - \lambda_2$. Since $\lambda_1, \lambda_2 \neq 0$ then $\mu \neq 0, 1$ is a proper fuzzy quasi e -clopen set of X . This shows that X has a proper fuzzy quasi e -clopen set. Therefore (X, τ_1, τ_2) is not fuzzy quasi e -connected.

Sufficiency: Suppose that (X, τ_1, τ_2) is not fuzzy quasi e -connected. Then there exists a proper fuzzy set μ , (say) in X such that μ is fuzzy quasi e -clopen. Since μ is proper it is easy to find non-zero fuzzy sets λ_1, λ_2 in X such that $\lambda_1 \leq \mu \leq 1 - \lambda_2$. This implies that (X, τ_1, τ_2) is not fuzzy quasi e -connected between λ_1 and λ_2 . \square

Proposition 4.10. A fbts (X, τ_1, τ_2) is said to be fuzzy quasi e^* (resp. a , β , δp and δs)-connected iff it is fuzzy quasi e^* (resp. a , β , δp and δs)-connected between each pair of its non-zero fuzzy sets λ_1 and λ_2 .

Proof. Follows from Proposition 4.9 \square

Proposition 4.11. For a non-empty subset Y of X let $(Y, \tau_1/Y, \tau_2/Y)$ be a subspace of the fbts (X, τ_1, τ_2) and let λ_1 and λ_2 be fuzzy sets of Y . If $(Y, \tau_1/Y, \tau_2/Y)$ is fuzzy quasi e (resp. e^* , a , β , δp and δs)-connected between the fuzzy sets λ_1 and λ_2 then (X, τ_1, τ_2) is also fuzzy quasi e (resp. e^* , a , β , δp and δs)-connected between its fuzzy sets λ_1^* and λ_2^* , where $\lambda_1^* : X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is such that

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda_1^*(x) &= \lambda_1(x) \text{ if } x \in Y \\ &= 0 \text{ if } x \in X \setminus Y \end{aligned}$$

and $\lambda_2^* : X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is such that

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda_2^*(x) &= \lambda_2(x) \text{ if } x \in Y \\ &= 0 \text{ if } x \in X \setminus Y. \end{aligned}$$

Proposition 4.12. In a fbts (X, τ_1, τ_2) let $(Y, \tau_1/Y, \tau_2/Y)$ be a fuzzy subspace for a non-empty subset Y of X such that χ_Y is fuzzy e -clopen set in (X, τ_1, τ_2) and let δ_1 and δ_2 be fuzzy sets of Y . If $(Y, \tau_1/Y, \tau_2/Y)$ is fuzzy quasi e -connected between δ_1 and δ_2 then (X, τ_1, τ_2) is also fuzzy quasi e -connected between δ_1 and δ_2 .

Proof. Suppose (X, τ_1, τ_2) is not fuzzy quasi e -connected between δ_1 and δ_2 . By construction χ_Y is fuzzy e -clopen in (X, τ_1, τ_2) and hence it is fuzzy quasi e -clopen in (X, τ_1, τ_2) . Then by our supposition on X we have

$$\delta_1 \leq \chi_Y \leq 1 - \delta_2 \quad (4.9)$$

holds true. Obviously, χ_Y is fuzzy e -clopen in $(Y, \tau_1/Y, \tau_2/Y)$, and it is fuzzy quasi e -clopen in $(Y, \tau_1/Y, \tau_2/Y)$.

As χ_Y in fuzzy quasi e -clopen in $(Y, \tau_1/Y, \tau_2/Y)$, the existence of the inequality (4.9) for fuzzy sets δ_1 and δ_2 in Y implies that $(Y, \tau_1/Y, \tau_2/Y)$ is not fuzzy quasi e -connected between δ_1 and δ_2 . \square

Proposition 4.13. In a fbts (X, τ_1, τ_2) let $(Y, \tau_1/Y, \tau_2/Y)$ be a fuzzy subspace for a non-empty subset Y of X such that χ_Y is fuzzy e^* (resp. a , β , δp and δs)-clopen set in (X, τ_1, τ_2) and let δ_1 and δ_2 be fuzzy sets of Y . If $(Y, \tau_1/Y, \tau_2/Y)$ is fuzzy quasi e^* (resp. a , β , δp and δs)-connected between δ_1 and δ_2 then (X, τ_1, τ_2) is also fuzzy quasi e^* (resp. a , β , δp and δs)-connected between δ_1 and δ_2 .

Proof. Follows from Proposition 4.12 \square

Proposition 4.14. Let (X, τ_1, τ_2) be a fuzzy bitopological space and let $Y \subset X$ be a non-empty subset of X such that χ_Y is fuzzy e (resp. e^* , a , β , δp and δs)-biopen set in (X, τ_1, τ_2) . Suppose that $(Y, \tau_1/Y, \tau_2/Y)$ be a fuzzy subspace of (X, τ_1, τ_2) . If (X, τ_1, τ_2) is fuzzy quasi e (resp. e^* , a , β , δp and δs)-connected between its fuzzy sets λ_1 and λ_2 , then $(Y, \tau_1/Y, \tau_2/Y)$ is also fuzzy quasi e (resp. e^* , a , β , δp and δs)-connected between λ_1/Y and λ_2/Y .

5. FUZZY QUASI e (RESP. e^* , a , β , δp , δs)-SEPARATED SETS IN FUZZY BITOPOLOGICAL SPACES

Definition 5.1. In a fbts (X, τ_1, τ_2) two fuzzy sets λ_1 and λ_2 are termed as

- (i) fuzzy quasi e -separated if $\lambda_1 \wedge fqeC1(\lambda_2) = 0 = fqeC1(\lambda_1) \wedge \lambda_2$.
- (ii) fuzzy quasi e^* -separated if $\lambda_1 \wedge fqe^*C1(\lambda_2) = 0 = fqe^*C1(\lambda_1) \wedge \lambda_2$.
- (iii) fuzzy quasi a -separated if $\lambda_1 \wedge fqaC1(\lambda_2) = 0 = fqaC1(\lambda_1) \wedge \lambda_2$.
- (iv) fuzzy quasi β -separated if $\lambda_1 \wedge fq\beta C1(\lambda_2) = 0 = fq\beta C1(\lambda_1) \wedge \lambda_2$.
- (v) fuzzy quasi δp -separated if $\lambda_1 \wedge fq\delta p C1(\lambda_2) = 0 = fq\delta p C1(\lambda_1) \wedge \lambda_2$.
- (vi) fuzzy quasi δs -separated if $\lambda_1 \wedge fq\delta s C1(\lambda_2) = 0 = fq\delta s C1(\lambda_1) \wedge \lambda_2$.

Proposition 5.1. Let λ_1 and λ_2 be $fqeo$ sets in a fbts (X, τ_1, τ_2) . If λ_1 and λ_2 are fuzzy quasi e -separated then $\lambda_1 \wedge \lambda_2 = 0$.

Proof. Suppose $\lambda_1 \wedge \lambda_2 \neq 0$. Then $\lambda_1 \neq 0$ and $\lambda_2 \neq 0$, and so $fqeC1(\lambda_1) \neq 0$, $fqeC1(\lambda_2) \neq 0$.

Therefore $\lambda_1 \wedge fqeC1(\lambda_2) \neq 0$ and $fqeC1(\lambda_1) \wedge \lambda_2 \neq 0$.

Thus we get $\lambda_1 \wedge fqeC1(\lambda_2) \neq 0 \neq fqeC1(\lambda_1) \wedge \lambda_2$ which shows that λ_1 and λ_2 are not fuzzy quasi e -separated. \square

Proposition 5.2. Let λ_1 and λ_2 be fqe^*o (resp. a , β , δp and δs) sets in a fbts (X, τ_1, τ_2) . If λ_1 and λ_2 are fuzzy quasi e^* (resp. a , β , δp and δs)-separated then $\lambda_1 \wedge \lambda_2 = 0$.

Proof. Follows from Proposition 5.1 \square

Proposition 5.3. If λ and μ , are fuzzy quasi e -separated sets and $\lambda \vee \mu$ is fuzzy biopen in a fbts (X, τ_1, τ_2) , then λ and μ , are fuzzy quasi e -open sets in (X, τ_1, τ_2) .

Proof. Since λ and μ are fuzzy quasi e -separated sets, $\lambda \wedge \mu = 0$. Then

$$\lambda = (\lambda \vee \mu) \wedge (1 - fqeCl(\lambda)). \quad (5.1)$$

Since $\lambda \vee \mu$ is fuzzy biopen set and $(1 - fqeCl(\lambda))$ is $fqeo$ set then, by Proposition 5.1, $(\lambda \vee \mu) \wedge (1 - fqeCl(\lambda))$ is fuzzy quasi e -open set and equivalently, λ is fuzzy quasi e -open set.

Similarly, from $\mu = (\lambda \vee \mu) \wedge (1 - fqeCl(\mu))$, we can prove that μ , is $fqeo$ set. Thus we get λ and μ , are $fqeo$ sets in (X, τ_1, τ_2) . \square

Proposition 5.4. If λ and μ , are fuzzy quasi e^* (resp. $a, \beta, \delta p$ and δs)-separated sets and $\lambda \vee \mu$ is fuzzy biopen in a fbts (X, τ_1, τ_2) , then λ and μ , are fuzzy quasi e^* (resp. $a, \beta, \delta p$ and δs)-open sets in (X, τ_1, τ_2) .

Proof. Follows from Proposition 5.3 \square

Proposition 5.5. Let $Y \subset X$ and ψ_Y be fuzzy biopen in (X, τ_1, τ_2) . If λ is fuzzy quasi e (resp. $e^*, a, \beta, \delta p$ and δs)-open in (X, τ_1, τ_2) then $\lambda \wedge \psi_Y$ is fuzzy quasi e (resp. $e^*, a, \beta, \delta p$ and δs)-open in the fuzzy subspace $(Y, \tau_1/Y, \tau_2/Y)$ of (X, τ_1, τ_2) .

Proposition 5.6. Let $(Y, \tau_1/Y, \tau_2/Y)$ be a fuzzy subspace of a fbts (X, τ_1, τ_2) . If λ is fuzzy quasi e (resp. $e^*, a, \beta, \delta p$ and δs)-open in $(Y, \tau_1/Y, \tau_2/Y)$ and ψ_Y is fuzzy biopen in (X, τ_1, τ_2) then λ is fuzzy quasi e (resp. $e^*, a, \beta, \delta p$ and δs)-open in (X, τ_1, τ_2) .

Proposition 5.7. Let $Y \subset X$ such that ψ_Y is fuzzy biopen in fbts (X, τ_1, τ_2) and $(Y, \tau_1/Y, \tau_2/Y)$ be fuzzy subspace of (X, τ_1, τ_2) and let λ_1 and λ_2 are two fuzzy sets on Y . Then λ_1 and λ_2 are fuzzy quasi e (resp. $e^*, a, \beta, \delta p$ and δs)-separated in (X, τ_1, τ_2) iff they are fuzzy quasi e (resp. $e^*, a, \beta, \delta p$ and δs)-separated in the subspace $(Y, \tau_1/Y, \tau_2/Y)$.

6. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we have introduced and studied fuzzy quasi e (resp. $e^*, a, \beta, \delta s$ and δp)-open sets, fuzzy quasi e (resp. $e^*, a, \beta, \delta s$ and δp)-closed sets, fuzzy quasi e (resp. $e^*, a, \beta, \delta s$ and δp)-connectedness between fuzzy sets fuzzy quasi e (resp. $e^*, a, \beta, \delta s$ and δp)-separated sets in fuzzy bitopological spaces and some properties and characterizations of them are investigated.

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